

iPhone SE Setup

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Setup by: Daniel Knott

Düsseldorf Institute for Competition Economics (DICE)

Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf

Before new Setup

Looking up browser

- Opening Safari browser
 - No choice screen appears
- When choosing search engine in settings, several options appear

Updating the phone

- Update to 17.4.1
- Upon opening Safari-Browser
 - Page with choices to set standard browser appears
 - Picking Safari-browser again as an option
 - Forwarded into App-Store. Upon opening Safari, it's set as the standard

More pictures on next slide

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About Your Default Browser

With iOS, you can choose your default web browser. By changing the default, you control which app opens when you open a website link.

You can change the default web browser at any time in Settings.

Continue

Choose Your Default Browser

SuSea, Inc.
You.com

Yandex LLC
Yandex

Microsoft Corporation
Edge

Aloha Mobile
Aloha

Mozilla
Firefox

Google
Chrome

<

Choose Your Default Browser

Mozilla
Firefox

Google
Chrome

Opera Software AS
Opera

Ecosia GmbH
Ecosia

DuckDuckGo, Inc.
DuckDuckGo

Mike Tigas
Onion Browser

Brave Software
Brave

Apple
Safari

Welcome to the App Store

A safe and trusted place to discover amazing apps and games, explore timely in-app events, and browse daily stories and recommendations by our editors.

Your searches, browsing, purchases and device trust score may be used to personalise your experience, send you notifications including for Apple marketing, improve the store and prevent fraud. [See how your data is managed...](#)

Continue

Cancel

Opening this app will set it as the default browser. You can always change this later in Settings.

Safari

Utilities

Open

7.5K RATINGS

4.1

AGE

17+

Years Old

CATEGORY

Utilities

ALL

IMAGES

Sign in

Google offered in: [Deutsch](#)

Germany

Dark theme: off

Settings

Privacy

Terms

AA

google.com

New Setup

Basic steps (pictures on the next slide)

- Pressing home button to choose language
 - Picked language: English
- Selecting country/region
 - Selected: Germany (already preselected)
- Choosing size and font of text
 - Default options retained
- Setup with other phone?
 - Opted not to
- Keyboard instructions
 - No customisation

Screenshots are not possible during the setup process, pictures taken with other phone

bonjour

Appuyez sur le bouton principal
pour ouvrir

Deutsch >

Français >

Nederlands >

Italiano >

Español >

Русский >

English >

Select Your Country or Region

Germany >

More Countries and Regions

Afghanistan >

Åland Islands >

Albania >

Algeria >

Appearance

Choose how you would like text and icons to look on iPhone.

Continue

Quick Start

Looking for nearby devices...

Bring your current iPhone or iPad near this iPhone to sign in and set up.

If your other iPhone or iPad doesn't show options for setting up this iPhone, make sure it's running iOS 11 or later, and has Bluetooth turned on. You can also set up this iPhone manually.

[Set Up Without Another Device](#)

Written and Spoken Languages

The following languages are commonly used in your region. You can set up your iPhone to use these settings or customise them individually.

Preferred Languages

English
German

Keyboards

English (UK)
Deutsch (Deutschland)
Emoji

Continue

[Customise Settings](#)

Choosing Wi-Fi network

- Picked the university Wi-Fi („eduroam“)
 - Logging in with student access
 - Asked to trust Wi-Fi network → „trust“

Data & Privacy

- Learn more: Offers specific information also offered on the website
- Continue

Set Up iPhone

- Set up for myself
- Not setting up Touch ID
- Creating passcode 123456
- Asked if to transfer apps and Data → dont transfer anything

Setting up Apple ID

Screenshots of Apple ID creation on following slides

- Dont have apple ID → set up anew
 - Create a free Apple ID
 - Name: DICE HHU
 - Date of birth: 10th April 2000
- Asked for E-Mail adress → do not have iCloud E-Mail → get a free iCloud E-Mail
 - dicephoneproject02@icloud.com
- Setting up Apple ID Password
 - Registration18.04
- Verification by phone number: my private phone number
 - Verification via text message

< Back

Apple ID

Forgot Password or Apple ID >

Create a Free Apple ID >

Set Up Later in Settings >

What is an Apple ID?

An Apple ID is the account you use to access everything Apple. You can sign in to all Apple services with a single Apple ID and password.

Get all your content on all your devices automatically, with iCloud.

Find the best selection of apps in the App Store.

Shop for music, movies, TV shows and more in the iTunes Store

< Back

Apple ID

Sign in with an email or phone number to use iCloud, the App Store and other Apple services.

Email or Phone Number

[Forgot password or don't have an Apple ID?](#)

Your Apple ID information is used to enable Apple services when you sign in, including iCloud Backup, which automatically backs up the data on your device in case you need to replace or restore it. Your device serial number may be used to check eligibility for service offers. [See how your data is managed...](#)

Continue

[Other Sign-In Options](#)

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01 01 01

DICE

HHU

Date of birth 10.04.00

April 2000 < >

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
					1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30

Continue

Terms and conditions

- Agree to
- Also sent by E-Mail

Further services

- Automatic updates → continue
- Location service → enable
- Set up mobile service → set up later in settings
- Screen time → set up later in settings
- Analytics → don't share
- Light or dark display → light

Screenshots on the following slides

[Back](#)

Screen Time

Get a weekly report with insights about your screen time and set time limits for apps you want to manage. You can also use Screen Time on children's devices and set up parental controls.

[Continue](#)[Set Up Later in Settings](#)[Back](#)

Analytics

Help Apple improve its products and services, including Siri and other intelligent features, by allowing analytics of usage and data from your iPhone and iCloud account. You can change your decision later in Settings.

All analysis is performed using privacy preserving techniques such as differential privacy and is not associated with you or your account.

[Learn More...](#)[Share with Apple](#)[Don't Share](#)[Back](#)

Light or Dark Display

Select a light or dark appearance and see how iPhone adjusts depending on which one you choose.

Light

Dark

Auto

[Continue](#)

Home screen and standard apps

- Notable preinstalled apps by apple
 - Facetime
 - Apple TV
 - Safari Browser (only browser installed)
 - Apple app store
 - Apple maps
 - Apple podcasts
 - iTunes
 - Etc...

First time opening Safari

Screenshots on the following slides

- Turn on Siri? → Not now
- Option offered to pick default browser from a range of options
 - Opera, Firefox, Ecosia, etc...
 - Trying a different Browser than Safari: DuckDuckGo
 - Forwarded into AppStore
 - Offered to download DuckDuckGo
 - Information: Opening of Browser will set as standard → cancel
 - Picking Safari (no download necessary)

Siri

Siri helps you find information and get things done, just by asking.

To use Siri, press and hold the Home button. Speak when Siri appears.

Apple stores transcripts of your interactions with Siri and may review a subset of these transcripts. Siri also sends information like your voice input, "Hey Siri" setup, contacts and location to Apple to process your request. Data is not associated with your Apple ID. [About Siri...](#)

Turn On Siri

Not Now

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- Yandex LLC
Yandex >
- Opera Software AS
Opera >
- SuSea, Inc.
You.com >
- Mike Tigas
Onion Browser >
- Mozilla
Firefox >
- Ecosia GmbH
Ecosia >
-

< Choose Your Default Browser

- Mozilla
Firefox >
- Ecosia GmbH
Ecosia >
- Apple
Safari >
- Google
Chrome >
- Aloha Mobile
Aloha >
- Microsoft Corporation
Edge >
- Brave Software
Brave >
- DuckDuckGo, Inc.
DuckDuckGo >

Welcome to the App Store

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Continue

Cancel

Opening this app will set it as the default browser. You can always change this later in Settings.

DuckDuckGo Private Browser

Privacy, simplified.

Get

In-App Purchases

63K RATINGS

4.8

AGE

17+

Years Old

CHART

No. 14

Utilities

DEVELOPER

Duck

Privacy, simplified.

Search, browse, and email more privately.

12:22

Search or enter address

Private Search

Search anonymously. We don't track you. Ever.

12:22

Coffee near me

ANONYMOUS LOCATION

Cancel

Opening this app will set it as the default browser. You can always change this later in Settings.

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Apple

First search in browser

- Upon tapping on search bar: information about personalised suggestions → continue
- First search: dice hhu
 - Asked to accept cookies from google → reject all

 EN Sign in

Before you continue to Google

We use [cookies](#) and data to

- Deliver and maintain Google services
- Track outages and protect against spam, fraud and abuse
- Measure audience engagement and site statistics to understand how our services are used and enhance the quality of those services

If you choose to 'Accept all', we will also use cookies and data to

- Develop and improve new services
- Deliver and measure the effectiveness of ads
- Show personalised content,

Results for **40225 Düsseldorf-Stadtbezirk 3** ·
[Choose area](#)

<https://www.dice.hhu.de>

hhu (Dice)
 Das Düsseldorf Institute for Competition Economics (DICE) ist ein Institut an der wirtschaftswissenschaftlichen Fakultät der...

Team

Düsseldorf Institute

Default cloud storage: iCloud

- Many apps are by default connected to iCloud

First time opening App Store

- Allow App Store to use location (location already shown) – allow while using app
- Some recommended apps but no other E-Mail programmes or browsers

First time opening E-Mail

- Protect Mail activity
- Allow notifications
- E-Mail is connected to Apple ID

Attempting to download an App from outside the app store

- Trying to download telegram messenger through chip.de
 - Tapping download forwards into app store
 - „open in Safari“ doesnt work either
- Download circumventing App-Store still not (easily) possible

Screenshots on next slide

HOME > ... > ... > IPHONE-APPS > SOCIAL NETWORKS

Telegram Messenger iPhone- / iPad-App

Version 10.10.1 | Rang 4 / 320 bei CHIP
in der Kategorie: Social Networks

DOWNLOAD
TELEGRAM MESSENGER IPHONE- / IPAD-
APP

✓ Kostenlos

Real chip.de ble

Telegram Messenger

Telegram FZ-LLC

Get

In-App
Purchases

16K RATINGS

3.7

AGE

17+

Years Old

CHART

No.3

Social Networking Te

Today

Games

Apps

Arcade

Search

Significant Changes

- In accordance with the newly enacted EU-regulations, Apple now offers a variety of browsers to be set as the main browser upon opening Safari the first time.
 - Safari however retains a significant advantage by being preinstalled and also having it's icon on display upon opening the phone immediately
- Apple still does not allow apps to be installed through other venues than the app store

